

Operation of an Hybrid PV-Battery System with Improved Harmonic Performance

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Abstract—The search of efficient, robust and fault-tolerant electronic power converters is a challenge for the industry and academia. Nowadays, the integration and exploitation of the renewable energy sources and energy storage systems is required. In these terms, the multilevel power converters and specifically the cascaded H-bridge (CHB) power converter is a very good candidate. However, if a CHB power converter operates under an unbalanced operation a low-frequency high-distortion content appears in the output voltage spectrum.

In order to reduce this problem, an extra cell, equipped with a low voltage battery or supercapacitor, is added to the original CHB converter. The idea is to operate the extra cell with the convenient duty cycle value in order to eliminate the low-order harmonic distortion generated by the unbalanced operation. This makes the proposed method very interesting because it leads to a reduction of the grid connection filter.

I. INTRODUCTION

The search of efficient, robust and fault-tolerant electronic power converters is a challenge for the industry and academia [1]. In addition, in the present and future energy scenario, the integration and exploitation of the renewable energy sources and energy storage systems (ESS) is required. In this way, the multilevel power converters have undergone a great development in the last decades [2]–[4]. The cascaded H-bridge (CHB) power converter is a very good candidate to achieve these objectives [5], [6]. This topology is composed by the connection in series of H-bridges with independent dc voltage sources as power supplies. This fact, is normally considered as a major drawback. However, it permits to connect in each power cell a dc power supply with different nature. For instance, it is possible to use independent photovoltaic arrays or combine them with batteries or super-capacitors in order to store the surplus energy [7]–[10]. To illustrate the idea, a two-cell CHB power converter is presented in Fig. 1.

II. CONVENTIONAL TWO-CELL CHB POWER CONVERTER OPERATION

To control the two-cell CHB power converter, one of many controller schemes presented in the literature is shown in Fig. 2 [11]. This controller structure is based on three different sequential stages. The first one is devoted to regulate the dc capacitor voltage of each cell using a simple, and robust, proportional plus integral linear controller. Besides, this stage

Fig. 1: Two-cell cascaded H-bridge power converter for a photovoltaic energy application

also provides the global RMS current reference required by the grid. On the other hand, using the estimated active power values provided by the previous stage, the voltage ratio control loop calculates the reference voltage that is needed to be modulated by each single cell in order to obtain the desired active power. Finally, there is an inner control loop to track the instantaneous current reference. The current control loop was presented in [12] and it is composed by a proportional term plus a repetitive controller which estimates the voltage droop in the smoothing inductor.

Using the control strategy represented in Fig. 2, it is possible to control each capacitor voltage individually and hence, this controller scheme is suitable to implement individual maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithms for a PV application. Therefore, an optimum maximum power of each PV-array connected to the power converter is obtained and the global system performance is increased [13].

On the other hand, to operate the CHB converter properly, it is usual to use the well-known phase-shifted pulse width modulation (PS-PWM) method [14]. This modulation technique requires a fixed phase displacement angle carrier between consecutive power cells. Taking into account this fact, for a M -cell CHB power converter the phase displacement is $360^\circ/M$. However, is normally the phase displacement is divided by 2 because it is common to consider for each power cell an unipolar modulation. In general, a CHB power converter operated with a PS-PWM technique presents the following advantages:

Fig. 2: Proposed control scheme for a two-cell CHB power converter

- Balanced power distribution in each H-bridge
- Equalization of power losses between the H-bridges
- Multiplicative effect of the effective switching frequency of the output voltage. It is located at M times (M is the number of H-bridges of the CHB) the frequency of an unipolar PWM technique (which is two times the triangular carrier frequency f_{pwm})

III. PROBLEM AND MOTIVATION

It has to be noticed that using individual MPPT controllers for each power cell leads to an asymmetric operation of the CHB converter. For instance, if the CHB converter has PV arrays connected to each H-bridge and the solar irradiations are unequal, the steady state capacitor voltage reached by the each MPPT controller will be different. Another reasons to obtain an unbalanced operation can be the dust, that are accumulated over the surface of the PV array as well as the well-known partial shading and temperature effect [13].

The consequences of the asymmetrical operation of the CHB converter have been deeply studied in [15]–[18]. It is demonstrated that this asymmetric operation provokes a harmonic distortion content located at twice the carrier frequency and its multiples because the properties of PS-PWM are partially lost.

In [16], the harmonic analysis using a variable-angle PS-PWM method for a three-cell CHB power converter was presented. However, in the case of the two-cell CHB is impossible to find a solution to eliminate the harmonic distortion located at $2f_{pwm}$. The reason of this fact is purely algebraic because the sum of two vectors can only be equal to zero if both vectors have the same module, the same direction and opposite orientation. It is clear that under an asymmetric operation, considering a two-cell CHB power converter the voltage vectors generated by the power cells have different modules.

In order to solve this problem different approaches can be addressed:

Fig. 3: Two-cell cascaded H-bridge power converter for a PV application with a extra power cell to control the harmonic distortion at $2f_{pwm}$

- 1) To add an extra DC-DC power converter stage between each PV array and the power cell of the CHB converter. In this way, the global control scheme will be decoupled. On one hand the H-bridge capacitor voltage is controlled by the control algorithm presented in Fig. 2 and the MPPT technique will be implemented by the DC-DC stage. The DC-DC converter could be based on boost, flyback or dual active bridge with high-frequency transformer topologies [19]. However, this proposal adds hardware complexity and is more expensive. In addition, the global efficiency is decreased because the complete system presents extra power losses.
- 2) To increase the order of the output filter in order to fulfill the grid code. Nevertheless, if the switching frequency is low, the design of the output filter can be difficult because the filter cut frequency is close to the grid frequency. Besides, the filter cost will be more expensive

and the passive elements can be more bulky and heavy.

- 3) To add an extra H-bridge in the power converter, connected to a small low-voltage battery or super-capacitor, in order to get an extra degree of freedom. This solution is presented in Fig. 3.

This paper is focused in the analysis of third solution in order to eliminate the first low-order distortion in the output voltage. In order to clarify the nomenclature, the extra cell connected to a battery will be called B-HB in the analysis.

IV. HARMONIC ANALYSIS OF HYBRID THREE-CELL PV-BATTERY CONVERTER

The total output voltage of a M -cell CHB power converter can be expressed, using the Fourier expansion series [16], as:

$$v(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M v_m(t) \simeq \sum_{m=1}^M \left(V_{dc,m} D_m + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[h_{mn} \cos(n\omega t + n\phi_m) \right] \right) \quad (1)$$

Where $V_{dc,m}$ and D_m are the capacitor voltage and duty cycle applied to m -th cell, respectively. Besides, h_{mn} represents the n -th harmonic coefficient generated by the m -th cell. It can be calculated as:

$$h_{mn} = \frac{2V_{dc,m}}{n\pi} \sin(n\pi D_m) \quad (2)$$

If the number of cells is $M = 3$, two active cells and the B-HB cell, the first carrier harmonic decomposition can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} h_{11} + h_{12} \cos(\phi_2) + h_{13} \cos(\phi_3) &= 0 \\ h_{12} \sin(\phi_2) + h_{13} \sin(\phi_3) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Keeping in mind the conventional PS-PWM method for a two-cell CHB converter, it is clear that (3) can be strongly simplified because the phase displacement angles set applied are $\phi_1 = 0^\circ$ and $\phi_2 = 180^\circ$. Therefore, introducing the coefficients given by (2) into (3) and applying the traditional angles values, the second equation in (3) system can be eliminated. The final expression can be re-written as:

$$V_{dc1} \sin(\pi D_1) - V_{dc2} \sin(\pi D_2) + V_{dc3} \sin(\pi D_3) \cos(\phi_3) = 0 \quad (4)$$

According to (4), the D_3 value to be applied in the B-HB to solve the system depends on ϕ_3 . Considering values $\phi_3 = 0^\circ$ or 180° , there are two different solutions:

$$D_3 = \frac{1}{\pi} \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{V_{dc2} \sin(\pi D_2) - V_{dc1} \sin(\pi D_1)}{V_{dc3}} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$D_3 = \frac{1}{\pi} \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{V_{dc1} \sin(\pi D_1) - V_{dc2} \sin(\pi D_2)}{V_{dc3}} \right) \quad (6)$$

The solution given by (5) is valid when $\phi_3 = 0^\circ$ and expression (6) is valid if ϕ_3 is set to 180° . It is not possible to consider another value of ϕ_3 because the $\sin(\phi_3) \neq 0$ and the second equation in (3) would not have solution.

On the other hand, the minimum voltage needed, in each sampling time, in the B-HB cell to solve the equation system is proportional to the operation point mismatch which is given by:

$$V_{dc3} = \left\| \left(V_{dc1} \sin(\pi D_1) - V_{dc2} \sin(\pi D_2) \right) \right\| \quad (7)$$

From (5) and (6) some considerations can be addressed. Firstly, the B-HB cell only will be operative if the active PV power cells are working creating an asymmetric operation of the CHB. Opposite to this, if both active cells are operate in the same operation point, the $D_x = \frac{\sin^{-1}(x)}{\pi}$ is equal to 0 and hence the extra cell can be bypassed. In this way, the power losses will be minimized. Besides, taking into account (7), the minimum dc voltage depends on the operating point error. Therefore, the B-HB power supply can be composed by a low-voltage battery or super-capacitor and the controller scheme deployed in the power converter would operate to maintain the battery state of charge (SoC) or the super-capacitor voltage.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to validate the proposal performance, some simulations have been developed. The results can be summarized into two different scenarios:

- A CHB power converter feeding a RL load.
- A grid-connected CHB power converter used for solar PV application.

A. Drive connected to an RL load results

The three-cell CHB power converter (two active cells plus the B-HB cell) is operated as a drive feeding a RL load under an asymmetric operation. In this scenario, and as example, the different dc voltages of the H-bridges have been set to 100, 120 (active cells) and 48 volts (battery powered B-HB cell) respectively. On the other hand, the modulation indexes applied are 0.9, 0.8 (active cells) and 0 (B-HB cell). Under this condition, applying a conventional PS-PWM modulation technique, as discussed previously a high-level distortion located at 2 kHz in the output voltage appears and the standard provide by the EN50160-2015 is not fulfilled. To clarify this situation, in Fig. 4a it is possible to observe the output voltage spectrum under asymmetric operation point using PS-PWM modulation (red bars) and the grid code provided by the EN50160-2015 (green line). This fact is possible to be observed in Fig. 4b where the total time-harmonic content is plotted and Fig. 4c shows the duty cycles used.

From $t = 50ms$, the B-HB cell is operated using the proposed strategy applying duty cycles D_3 determined by (5) and (6). According to (7), the maximum voltage needed in the battery to solve this asymmetric operation is

$$V_{bat} = \left\| \left(100 \sin(\pi 0.9) - 120 \sin(\pi 0.8) \right) \right\| = 39.63V \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4: a) Output voltage spectrum for a three-cell CHB converter using the traditional PS-PWM with the B-HB cell bypassed (red bars) and operating the B-HB cell properly in a inverter operation (solid blue bars), EN50160-2015 standard (green line). b) Harmonic content waveform in the output voltage. c) Duty cycles applied to the system under the both strategies

and hence, it is possible to find a valid solution with the 48 volts of the battery. As can be observed in Fig. 4a (drawn in blue bars) and Fig. 4b the first harmonic voltage content has been eliminated and the standard is completely fulfilled. The duty cycle D_3 applied, every sampling time, is represented in Fig. 4c.

B. PV Grid-connected results

For the PV grid-connected application, the most relevant controller parameters and passive elements used in the simulation are shown in Table I. The MPPT voltage value for each PV array under different irradiation values are 175 and 200 volts (active cells) and 48 volts (B-HB cell). The total simulation time is 1s and it is split off in three different parts.

TABLE I: Parameters of the PV system and control scheme

Parameter	Value
Nominal power (kW)	4
Cell switching frequency (kHz)	2
Smooth inductor (mH)	5
Cell DC Capacitance (mF)	2.2
Power PV array (kW)	2
Irradiance (kW/m ²)	1
Battery nominal voltage (V)	48
Battery capacity (Ah)	5.4
Battery SoC (%)	75
k_{pV}	0.3
k_{iV}	6
k_{pC}	2
k_1, k_2	0.5
k_r	1.2
Filter Notch frequency (Hz)	100
Filter Quality factor	0.707

The complete simulation result can be observed in Fig. 5 and summarized as:

- 1) Until $t = 500ms$, the power converter is operated conventionally in order to reach the nominal operation point. Each dc capacitor voltage reference, fixed by the MPPT controller scheme, are 200 and 175 volts respectively. The B-HB cell is bypassed and hence it exists a harmonic content located at $2kHz$ due to the asymmetric operation point. The output voltage spectrum is drawn in Fig. 6 (red bars).
- 2) From $t = 500ms$ to $t = 700ms$, the B-HB cell starts to operate using (5). The B-HB cell works applying the duty cycle D_3 in order to eliminate the first harmonic content and is able to absorb the surplus power that creates the asymmetric operation. The B-HB operation does not affect to the overall system behavior and, as can be seen in Fig. 5, the capacitors reach the desired voltages in steady state. The duty cycle D_3 applied in B-HB cell is shown in Fig. 5. On the other hand, the output voltage spectrum is represented in Fig. 6, in solid blue bars. It is possible to see that the distortion located at $2kHz$ is totally cleared.
- 3) Finally since $t = 700ms$, the B-HB cell is operated using (6). In this case, the B-HB cell acts supplying the power needed to eliminate the harmonic content at $2kHz$. It must be noticed that the output voltage spectrum is not represented because the extra cell behavior using (6) presents a similar result compared with Fig. 6.

From the simulation results, it is possible to conclude that the average power absorbed and delivered by the battery is $167.65W$ and $180.65W$ using solutions denoted by (5) and (6) respectively. Theses numbers represent the 4.20% and 4.50% of the $4kW$ nominal power. In this way, it is possible to

Fig. 5: Hybrid PV-battery power converter simulation summary. From top to bottom: output voltage, grid current (blue) and reference grid current (red), dc capacitor voltages (blue and red) and reference dc voltages (yellow and purple) and duty cycles for active cells (blue and red) and duty cycle for the B-HB cell (yellow)

operate the system using both solutions in an alternating way so the battery SoC is handled properly.

Finally, several simulations have been performed under different asymmetrical operation points. The ratios between the nominal power handled by the power converter and power provided or absorbed by the battery cell are shown in Fig. 7. The number between square brackets representing the number of PV arrays connected in parallel. It can be observed that for each solar irradiation (λ_i) there is a constant relation between the power managed by the overall system and the battery.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The cascaded H-bridge (CHB) power converters usually are operated using the conventional PS-PWM modulation technique because presents several advantages such as equal distribution of power losses and active power. Besides, it is well-known its multiplicative effect in terms of frequency in the output voltage. Nevertheless, under unbalanced operation the benefits of this modulation technique are partially lost. These unbalanced conditions appear when the CHB converter

is considered for PV applications or when dc sources with different nature are used for each H-bridge. In this case, a harmonic distortion is present at $2f_{pwm}$.

In order to reduce this problem, an extra cell, equipped with a low voltage battery or supercapacitor, is added to the original CHB power converter. The idea is to operate the extra cell in a proper way in order to eliminate the low-order harmonic distortion generated by the unbalanced operation. Besides, if a balanced operation is performed, the extra cell can be bypassed. The state of charge of the battery connected to the extra cell has been also addressed. These facts make the proposal very interesting because it leads to a reduction of the grid connection filter.

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Fig. 6: Output voltage spectrum for a three-cell CHB converter using the traditional PS-PWM with the B-HB cell bypassed (red bars) and operating the B-HB cell properly in a grid-connected operation (solid blue bars)

Fig. 7: Comparison performed for two different operation points (λ_1 and λ_2) between the power delivered (diamond marks) or absorbed (square marks) by the battery and the nominal power handled by the power converter.

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